

Flexcrash

D6.1 Risk Management Plan

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Revision History

Vers ion	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	01/02/2023	Simona Neri (EUT)	Draft version circulated to partners together with the risklog
1.0	18/02/2023	Begoña Casas (EUT)	Revision
2.0	22/02/2022	Simona Neri (EUT)	Format, revision

Executive Summary

This report is an update of DoA preliminary risk assessment and aims at performing a continuous check of the risks than can occur during the project implementation. This allows the absorption of the proper measure to mitigate the risk before it occurs. The activities that have been performed are the following: - Follow-up of risks (identified at the beginning of the project (DoA) - Identification of new risks arising during the course of the project; - Identification and/or implementation of contingency plans for initial and/or new risks; - Identification and/or implementation of corrective measures for initial and/or new risks

Table of Contents

<i>Revision History</i>	2
<i>Executive Summary</i>	2
<i>Table of Contents</i>	3
<i>Terminology and Acronyms</i>	4
<i>1. Introduction</i>	5
<i>2. Overview FLEXCRASH risk management approach</i>	6
<i>3. FLEXCRASH risks identification, contingency plans and corrective measures</i>	7
3.1 Month 0.....	8
3.2 Month 6.....	10
<i>4. Conclusions</i>	12

Terminology and Acronyms

GA	<i>General Assembly</i>
RO	<i>Risk holders</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Introduction

A Risk Assessment is an important tool for Project managers to use in evaluating the safety of the project that they manage, and in determining the potential for loss or harm to organizational operations, mission, and stakeholders. Risk can never be totally eliminated but can be minimized by the application of proper measures. The decision as to what level risk will be accepted will be based on management review of the identified solutions needed to mitigate risk versus the potential impact of implementing those controls on available resources and system operations. The Risk Assessment identifies the current level of risk for the project and provides risk mitigation recommendations for management review. This risk assessment describes FLEXCRASH vulnerabilities and associated threats based on executive, legislative, departmental, and technical guidelines. The purpose of this report is to provide Project managers with an assessment of the adequacy of the management, operational and technical controls that are currently in place to secure FLEXCRASH. It also evaluates the likelihood that vulnerability can be exploited, assesses the impact associated with these threats and vulnerabilities, and identifies the overall risk level. This document pretends to give an update on the status of the risks identified in the proposal stage and the contingency measures that have been put in place so far as well as new potential risks that have been identified in the last 6 months of project implementation.

This deliverable has been created by Project coordinator Simona Neri with the support of the Begoña Casas, technical coordinator and the proposal and project coordination Department based on common best coordination practices in Eurecat that has served as a common tool kit reference for H2020 projects and have continuity in Horizon Europe that are coordinated by this entity. Some sections concerning the management of Horizon Europe projects and that are common to other similar have been directly taken from our internal Project Handbook text.

2. Overview FLEXCRASH risk management approach

Roles and Responsibilities.

Project coordinators and work-package leaders are in charge of risk management governance. **Project Coordinator oversees the entire risk management** system with project implementation. He updates support documentation if necessary and coordinated all risk management activities by collecting and managing all information, suggesting risk mitigation activities and reporting risk and mitigation action status (contingency planning).

The Project Coordinator acts as the integrator of the risk management functions across all concerned project domains and WP. The Project Coordinator also reports the results of the risk management task to the next higher level in the project hierarchy (Project Steering Board).

WP leaders will act as Risk Holders (RO) and therefore pay attention to the WP-related risks they lead. The WP leaders will control the risks by implementing the contingency measures and the risk assessment related to the WP they lead. If necessary, they will inform of any potential new risk detected and will propose contingency measures to the Project Coordinator and the Steering Committee.

Risk Management Procedure

The risk management approach adopted in the project is composed by two main phases:

- Assessment: this phase consists on the monitoring and identification of project risks;
- Implementation: this phase consists on the definition of contingency measures and corrective actions.

Figure 1. Risk Management procedure in FLEXCRASH

Risk monitoring

WP leaders but also, of all FLEXCRASH partners are responsible to communicate to the Project Coordinator about the status of any potential risk as well as its mitigation plan. Risk exposure will be continuously re-evaluated and modified according to the following Risk Matrix.

IMPACT	High	Medium	High	High
	Medium	Low	Medium	High
	Low	Low	Low	Medium
		Low	Medium	High
		LIKELIHOOD		

Figure 2. Risk Matrix

The risk management monitoring process is iterated on a six-months basis to ensure that:

- Identified risks are continuously monitored until judged acceptable;
- Regular evaluation is performed to identify new sources of risks;
- Regular update of the Risk Status Report includes risk mitigation actions;
- Risk mitigation actions are performed and monitored.

Risk-mitigation measures

Each WP leader is responsible for executing the risk mitigation activities which relate to the WP they lead. An item can be considered closed when the risk-mitigation measures have been implemented and a new exposure risk is estimated as low following the Risk Matrix (Figure 2).

3. FLEXCRASH risks identification, contingency plans and corrective measures

Section 3 is divided in two subsections. 3.1) reports a brief overview of the risks as identified at the beginning of the project and updated in every risk report. 3.2) reports the evolution of a single risk during time together with contingency plans and corrective actions, if any.

Overview of periodic risks identification

This section gives an overview of FLEXCRASH risks at M0 and M6. Risks are numbered in a sequential order starting from the ones as reported in the Risk Tab of the Participant Portal together with linked to their Critical risks-mitigation measures. Correlation among risks and WPs is provided as well so that it is clear which WP the risk mainly belongs to and impacts to.

Contingency measures and corrective actions (if any) for each of these risks, as well as their evolution during time

3.1 Month 0

The risks at M0 are those reported in the Portal See below the list of risks and the WP that involve:

Risk Nº	Person that has identified the risk	Date when it was raised	Description of risk
1	Kurzböck, Christian	Apr-21	The identified future mixed traffic scenarios may not be representative (M,M)
2	Kurzböck, Christian	Apr-21	The developed material models for HPDC shall be calibrated by casted samples with complex geometries to reflect real mechanical behaviour (M,M)
3	Kurzböck, Christia Begoña Casas	Apr-21	The material models shall be validated by lab-scale high-speed crash tests. The maximum capacity of the testing equipment is 100 kN, which may be too low (M,M)
4	Begoña Casas	Apr-21	Possible crack local fatal formation by the direct metal deposition at the interface of preforms of thickness below 2mm (M,M)
5	Begoña Casas	Apr-21	Plastic deformation of substrate by metal deposition (M,H)
6	Begoña Casas	Apr-21	Advanced test for toughness and fatigue for AVFF are not as easy as those developed for AHSS (L,L)
7	Natalia Carmona	Apr-21	Acceptance reluctance by OEM and component makers at integrating the LMD manufacturing within the welding automated station (M,H)
8	Juan Jose Matarranz	Apr-21	Resource saving goals cannot be fully reached (M/M)
9	Simona Neri	Apr-21	Change of beneficiary (ies) in the implementation phase (M, H)
10	Simona Neri	Apr-21	Conflict among partners (L,H)

Table 1. Overview of FLEXCRASH risks at Month 0

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	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
R1	x					
R2	x					
R3	x	x				
R4		x				
R5		x				
R6		x				
R7					x	
R8				x		
R9	x	x	x	x	x	x
R10	x	x	x	x	x	x

Table 2. Overview of FLEXCRASH risks per WP at Month 0

3.2 Month 6

Risk N°	Person that identified the risk	Date when it was raised	Description of risk	related WP	Likelihood	Impact	Proximity of the risk	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	risk-mitigation measures Applied?	Comments
1	Kurzböck Christian	Apr-21	The identified future mixed traffic scenarios may not be representative (M,M)		1M	M		Reproduction of real critical scenarios and existing mixed traffic scenarios. Also capturing future scenarios using the multiplayer platform as AV/ADAS can be directly connected to it.	Yes	
2	Kurzböck Christian	Apr-21	The developed material models for HPDC shall be calibrated by casted samples with complex geometries to reflect real mechanical behaviour (M,M)		1M	M		Produce simple HPDC strips and use electric wire discharge to get the final complex geometries	Yes	
3	Kurzböck Christian, Begoña Casas	Apr-21	The material models shall be validated by lab-scale high-speed crash tests. The maximum capacity of the testing equipment is 100 kN, which may be too low (M,M)	1-2	M	M		Simulate the crash test to estimate the maximum reaction force. First solution: Re-design the samples (crash boxes) to reduce loads if needed. Second solution: Run crash tests at quasi-static conditions.	Yes	
4	Begoña Casas	Apr-21	Possible crack local fatal formation by the direct metal deposition at the interface of preforms of thickness below 2mm (M,M)		2M	M		Local thermal treatments to prepare the substrate (heating) and for fast solidification of the deposited material (cooling)	Yes	
5	Begoña Casas	Apr-21	Plastic deformation of substrate by metal deposition (M,H)		2M	H		The counter bending of preform will be consider resetting planarity (counter springback)	Yes	
6	Begoña Casas	Apr-21	Advanced test for toughness and fatigue for AVFF are not as easy as those developed for AHSS (L,L)		2L	L		The homogeneous properties of sheets through the volume allows to take measures from specimen surface. AVFF might show volumetric dependence. EUT is currently working in alternative measuring techniques, based on thermal or acoustic emissions with convincing results.	Yes	
7	Natalia Carmona	Apr-21	Acceptance reluctance by OEM and component makers at integrating the LMD manufacturing within the welding automated station (M,H)		5M	H		Wire based LMD will be considered to reduce the cleaning cost of the deposition station, the hybrid design will be taken into account the manufacturing/assembly constraints: type of station (very likely weldings), robotization of station (likely anthropomorphic), and production cadence time	Yes	
8	Juan Jose Matarranz	Apr-21	Resource saving goals cannot be fully reached (M/M)		4M	M		LCA will be conducted continuously during Flexcrash to define early measures for improved performance	Yes	
9	Simona Neri	Apr-21	Change of beneficiary (ies) in the implementation phase (M, H)	all	M	H		Reallocation of resources and ensuring sufficient competence of the consortium is maintained.	Yes	
10	Simona Neri	Apr-21	Conflict among partners (L,H)	all	L	H		Conflict resolution measures clearly assigned and agreed upon in the consortium agreement, and MoU signed at proposal stage. The conflict potentials will be minimized through control mechanisms in WP6.	Yes	
11	Francesco Bruzzo	Feb-23	Geometrical accuracy and internal material defects in complex AVFF produced by LMD		2M	L		Use and test only AVFF with easier geometries that favor the LMD process	Yes	
12	Natalia Carmona	Feb-23	Internal issues regarding IPR and Exploitation (specific for WP5 but aligned with risk n°10)		5L	H		Ownership and exploitation of results will be openly addressed and discussed in several occasions throughout the project with all partners (GA's, WP meetings, individual meetings...).	Yes	
13	Miriam Vendrell	Apr-22	Low participation in dissemination activities (low stakeholder engagement in webinars, workshops and local sessions)		5M	H	Month 40	Intensive communication campaigns promoting the activities through relevant channels will be run minimum 1 month in advance for project events. Take advantage of project partners involved in relevant EU projects and initiatives to serve as ambassadors of Flexcrash and multiply project dissemination and stakeholder engagement	Yes	
14	Miriam Vendrell	Apr-22	The audience has difficulty to understand Flexcrash solutions		5M	M	Month 40	Usage of real examples, plain language and adapt the technology and language to different contexts as well as the audience's needs.	Yes	
15	Miriam Vendrell	Feb-23	Not enough engagement on Flexcrash communication channels		5L	H	Month 40	Creation of more content for the project website and social media that engages stakeholders, increase the frequency of publication on project channels. Provision and collection of free-to-use pictures, videos and data for social media actions in Flexcrash - SharePoint folder.	Yes	
16	Christian Kurzböck	Feb-23	It is not possible to design a conceptual design of the active safety crash tolerant structure in the first year		1M	H	Month 40	Separation into individual functional assemblies and later combination into an overall front crash structure	Yes	
17	Andoni Agirre	Feb-23	The design and conclusions from previous WP are valid for a narrow range of crash impact angle; so extrapolation to other new crash-tolerant structures might not be evident		4M	M	Month 40	Perform robustness analysis during the development faces of previous WPs	Yes	
18	Daniele Pullini	Feb-23	The cost of DED powder material will not decrease enough to see a full adoption (by the whole body in white) by the automotive supply chain (tier1s and OEM)	all	M	L	Month 48	Monitor the R&D and marketplace outside the project during the project, and promote the adoption perspective by dissemination the AVFF concept throughout the different industrial sectors supply chain (from space and biomedical towards the larger volume industries)	Yes	Recycled Al powder property evolution is a very promising R&D field to monitor
19	Daniele Pullini	Feb-23	Distorsion of complex shape parts cannot be fully compensated by thermal treatment during and post deposition		3M	M/L	Month 36	New designing model needs to be developed to include part to be manufactured pre-deformation (reverse-eng.)	Yes	process and product modelling

Table 3. Overview of FLEXCRASH risks at Month 6

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
R1	x					
R2	x					
R3	x	x				
R4		x				
R5		x				
R6		x				
R7					x	
R8				x		
R9	x	x	x	x	x	x
R10	x	x	x	x	x	x
R11		x				
R12					x	
R13					x	
R14					x	
R15					x	
R16	x					
R17				x		
R18	x	x	x	x	x	x
R19			x			

Table 4. Overview of FLEXCRASH risks per WP at Month

Risks identification and implementation of contingency measures

The monthly WPs meetings and ad-hoc Consortium meeting dynamics have been maintained by Coordinator (EUT). All the members of the consortium have been asked to participate and to provide updates about both technical and administrative issues. These dynamics obliged the Consortium to reflect and share all the potential difficulties that they foresee can be face.

As for guidelines, at M6 the Work Package Leaders have gone through a formal risk analysis and reported to the Coordinator and this analysis will be shared during the review meeting. The outputs of this analysis have been described in this deliverable.

Most relevant risks identified at M6

In this section, the most relevant risks according to the risk matrix (see section 2.3) are presented. The criteria to consider these risks as “relevant” is: 1) high impact or high likelihood or 2) medium impact and medium likelihood.

4. Conclusions

This report testifies the deep analysis (performed at M6) of that risks that may arise during the project. The project Partners are continuously asked to revise and express any new ones during the recurrent technical meetings. Furthermore, during the official GA one session dedicated to risk has been assigned. In this way, the Consortium is actively working in order to avoid any major event that could affect both technical or financial aspects of the projects, allowing the smooth flow of the project implementation.

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